

OU process for modeling adaptive evolution

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In this tutorial, we demonstrate the use of the multi-optimum Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process for modeling adaptive evolution (i.e., the Hansen model). We expect readers to use this tutorial as a companion to our published paper (Moen *et al.* In review). Thus, we direct readers to the paper for more extensive discussion and references for the methods we demonstrate. Please note that the way we wrote the code, R objects will accumulate in your working environment. We formatted the tutorial this way to help you see steps more explicitly. This detailed structure causes the tutorial to appear long, but running the steps is straightforward and does not require much time. For ideas on options for more economic coding, please see our full analysis code, posted as Appendix S4 in this same Dryad submission (Moen *et al.* 2021).

In this tutorial we will analyze evolution of CT_{\min} in hylid frogs of Middle America. We first demonstrate how to set up the models of biogeographic changes, which we then implement in analyses of the Hansen model in packages *OUwie* and *ouch*. We then show users how accommodate uncertainty in ancestral states of selective environments with Bayesian stochastic mapping and how to incorporate that mapping into *OUwie*.

Loading data and packages

We will first load all the necessary R packages and data for this tutorial. We will also load a .R file that contains two custom functions used in the tutorial. You can open that file separately for additional details on the functions. We developed this tutorial with R version 4.0.2. It may not work well on previous versions of R.

```
library(OUwie) # Our principal package for OU analysis. Version 2.6.
library(ouch) # An alternative package for OU analysis. Version 2.17.
library(phytools) # Used here for stochastic mapping. Version 0.7-70.
library(tidyverse) # Suite of packages for data manipulation. Key included packages used
# in this tutorial are dplyr, tidyr, ggplot2, and purrr. Version 1.3.0.
source("AppendixS6_tutorial_functions.R") # Custom functions we wrote for this tutorial.
load("AppendixS7_OU_tutorial_data.RData") # R workspace with objects 'dat' and 'tree'
```

Let's take a look at the data we are working with:

```
dat # Print data frame
```

```
## # A tibble: 12 x 5
##   species_phylo      region  elevation CTmin CTmin_SE
##   <chr>             <chr>    <chr>    <dbl>  <dbl>
## 1 Exerodonta_abdivita tropical highland  6.33   0.27
## 2 Ptychohyla_zophodes tropical highland  5.14   0.23
## 3 Charadrahyla_nephila tropical highland  6.42   0.062
```

```
## 4 Hyla_cinerea      temperate temperate 3.55 0.08
## 5 Hyla_avivoca     temperate temperate 2.86 0.26
## 6 Hyla_arenicolor  temperate temperate 5.44 0.31
## 7 Tlalocohyla_smithii tropical lowland NA NA
## 8 Smilisca_cyanosticta tropical lowland 6.9 0.18
## 9 Smilisca_baudinii tropical lowland 8.92 0.9
## 10 Pseudacris_crucifer temperate temperate 0.64 1.26
## 11 Pseudacris_fouquettei temperate temperate 0.56 1.02
## 12 Acris_blancharidi temperate temperate 0.27 1.16
```

Setting up internal states and preparing data for analysis

The Hansen model requires specifying environments, or “regimes”, for all branches of the phylogeny. This means also specifying states for internal nodes, which we need to estimate. (The node states are then used to specify branch states; see discussion below on how *OUwie* and *ouch* differ in this respect). Researchers have many options for estimating these states, and all methods have advantages and disadvantages (see our paper’s discussion for more details). Here, our example hyloid dataset has only 12 of 191 species of the Middle-American clade (Faivovich *et al.* 2018; AmphibiaWeb 2021). To avoid possible error from low sampling, we will set internal regimes manually based on estimates from a previous study with much more extensive species sampling (Moen *et al.* 2009). Moreover, at the end of this tutorial we consider stochastic mapping of states, a common approach (but one that, like in this example dataset, may not work well when sampling <10% of a clade).

Here we set up internal states for our OU2 and OU3 models. The former has adaptive optima for temperate and tropical lineages, whereas the latter splits tropical lineages into highland and lowland types.

```
# Assign the values tropical-temperate to internal nodes
temptrop <- c(rep('tropical', 5), rep('temperate', 2),
             rep('tropical', 2), rep('temperate', 2))
tree_ou2 <- tree
tree_ou2$node.label <- temptrop

# Assign the values highland-lowland-temperate to internal nodes
highlow <- c('lowland', rep('highland', 3), 'lowland', rep('temperate', 2),
            rep('lowland', 2), rep('temperate', 2))
tree_ou3 <- tree
tree_ou3$node.label <- highlow
```

Let’s plot these states on the tree (Fig. 1) to ensure we correctly set the states of the internal nodes. We have no CT_{\min} data for *Tlalocohyla smithii*, so let’s also remove that species from our trees:

```
tree_ou2 <- drop.tip(tree_ou2, "Tlalocohyla_smithii")
tree_ou3 <- drop.tip(tree_ou3, "Tlalocohyla_smithii")
```

Lastly, let’s use the package *dplyr* to remove this species from our data (i.e. the only one without CT_{\min} data), remove the environmental variable unrelated to each analysis, and put the data frames in the format needed for *OUwie*.

```
dat_OU2 <- dat %>%
  dplyr::filter(!is.na(CTmin)) %>%
  select(-elevation) %>%
  data.frame()
dat_OU3 <- dat %>%
```


Figure 1: Map of OU regimes for *OUwie*. The left phylogeny maps OU2 regimes, while the right phylogeny maps OU3 regimes.

```
dplyr::filter(!is.na(CTmin)) %>%
  select(-region) %>%
  data.frame()
```

OUwie analysis

R has many packages that analyze the Hansen model with multiple discrete optima (Hansen 1997; Butler and King 2004). These packages include *ouch*, *OUwie*, *mvMORPH*, *slouch*, and *mvSLOUCH*. We focus here on *OUwie* because the package gives users the largest number of analysis options, including allowing stochastic character maps. We also demonstrate later how to use *ouch*, which has some distinct advantages (namely, speed) and disadvantages (namely, less user-friendly). We describe *ouch* in more detail below when implementing code.

For this tutorial we replicate analyses from our paper for CT_{\min} . We compare four models: standard Brownian motion (BM), a single-optimum OU model (OU1), an OU model with optima for temperate and tropical lineages (OU2), and an OU model with optima for temperate, tropical highland, and tropical lowland lineages (OU3). In all cases we assume a single pull parameter (α) and Brownian variance (σ^2) for the whole tree.

There are several options for analysis. First, we analyzed models with standard errors (SE) for CT_{\min} , as this improves model estimates when such SEs are available. Second, we scaled the tree to a total height of 1 million years. We have found in our previous work that this option can improve optimization, particularly at smaller values of σ^2 and α . It does not affect the values of the optima (θ_i), our focus in these analyses. Third, for OU models we used the option `root.station = TRUE` to assume the stationary value for the regime at the root of the tree. It is unclear whether this assumption is optimal (see discussion in Ho and Ané [2014], as well as *OUwie*'s documentation file 'OUwie_2.1_adds.pdf'). We used it here because it resulted in the most reasonable estimates of θ_i . Finally, we note that discrete environmental states are used in neither BM nor OU1; *OUwie*() simply ignores the discrete-trait column in the data frame and node labels when estimating these models. So we used the data frame `dat_OU2` and phylogeny `tree_ou2` for those models. Also note that *OUwie* will give a warning when estimating these models, given our number of species (it gives this warning anytime your number of species are less than ten times the number of estimated parameters).

```
# (a) Brownian motion
brown_OUwie <- OUwie(phy = tree_ou2, data = dat_OU2, model = "BM1", mserr = "known",
  scaleHeight = 1, root.station = F, algorithm = "invert", diagn = T)
# (b) Single-optimum OU
```

```

OU1_OUwie <- OUwie(phy = tree_ou2, data = dat_OU2, model = "OU1", mserr = "known",
  scaleHeight = 1, root.station = T, algorithm = "invert", diagn = T)
# (c) Temperate-tropical OU2
OU2_OUwie <- OUwie(phy = tree_ou2, data = dat_OU2, model = "OUM", mserr = "known",
  scaleHeight = 1, root.station = T, algorithm = "invert", diagn = T)
# (d) Highland tropical, lowland tropical, and temperate OU3
OU3_OUwie <- OUwie(phy = tree_ou3, data = dat_OU3, model = "OUM", mserr = "known",
  scaleHeight = 1, root.station = T, algorithm = "invert", diagn = T)

```

Now let's summarize the output. Normally we want to know things like number of free parameters, likelihood support for each model, AICc support, and the relative statistical support for each model. AICc is the small-sample version of the Akaike Information Criterion, and the relative support is measured by AICc weights (Burnham and Anderson 2002). We'll use our custom function `aicc_wgt_calc()` to calculate the AICc weights and various *tidyverse* packages to summarize the results.

```

# Put output objects into a list to more easily summarize results
all_out <- list(brown_OUwie, OU1_OUwie, OU2_OUwie, OU3_OUwie)
names(all_out) <- c("BM", "OU1", "OU2", "OU3")

# Summarize model fits
CTmin_fits <- tibble(model = names(all_out), k = map_dbl(all_out, ~.$param.count),
  loglik = map_dbl(all_out, ~.$loglik), AICc = map_dbl(all_out, ~.$AICc),
  wgt = aicc_wgt_calc(AICc))
CTmin_fits # Print results table

```

```

## # A tibble: 4 x 5
##   model    k loglik  AICc    wgt
##   <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 BM      2  -24.7  54.9 0.209
## 2 OU1     3  -25.9  61.2 0.00928
## 3 OU2     4  -18.9  52.4 0.729
## 4 OU3     5  -17.8  57.7 0.0530

```

OU2 is the most supported model by AICc (weight = 0.729), with Brownian motion also having reasonable statistical support (weight = 0.209). We also see that OU3 improves the log-likelihood a reasonable amount, but adding a fifth parameter with just 12 species exacts a large penalty for parameter number, increasing the AICc substantially.

We also should examine the parameter estimates. These estimates are arguably more important than the model fits for understanding the biological meaning of our results (Butler and King 2004; Beaulieu *et al.* 2012). They also help us to ask whether our model fits are reasonable. The key parameters to examine in an OU model are σ^2 , α , and θ_i . We should examine their maximum-likelihood estimates (MLEs) and their standard errors (SEs). Let's examine those of the optimal model, OU2.

```

# Summary of most model parameters, including MLEs and SEs of optima and
# MLEs of alpha and sigma squared
OU2_OUwie

```

```

##
## Fit
##      lnL      AIC      AICc      BIC model ntax
## -18.8878 45.7756 52.44227 47.36718  OUM  11

```

```

##
##
## Rates
##      temperate tropical
## alpha      1.062891 1.062891
## sigma.sq   3.378103 3.378103
##
## Optima
##      temperate tropical
## estimate -1.401420 6.5040829
## se       1.361705 0.7388736
##
##
## Half life (another way of reporting alpha)
## temperate tropical
## 0.6521339 0.6521339
##
## Arrived at a reliable solution

# Standard errors of alpha and sigma squared, as calculated from the
# curvature of the likelihood surface
OU2_OUwie$solution.se

##      temperate tropical
## alpha      0.8797636 0.8797636
## sigma.sq   0.8426928 0.8426928

```

Finally, we can check the reliability of our estimates of σ^2 and α with eigenanalysis of the likelihood surface. Positive eigenvalues indicate reliable parameter estimates. Note that you must use the option `diagn = TRUE` in your `OUwie()` fits in order to obtain these values.

```

OU2_OUwie$eigval

## [1] 6.10 0.76

```

Both are positive values, suggesting that the estimates of σ^2 and α are (statistically) reliable. Another option for examining the robustness of these estimates is to use parametric bootstrapping. We cover this option in our second tutorial, “Parametric bootstrapping for OU models”.

ouch analysis

There are many other good options for fitting the Hansen model in R, as we listed above. We encourage you to examine these packages and their pros and cons, which is beyond the scope of this tutorial. We simply want to acknowledge here that we are users—rather than authors—of these packages. There are more knowledgeable developers and other users who have put considerable time into writing papers, tutorials, help files, and R documentation to help users understand their methods. We want to encourage you to take advantage of their effort.

That said, we think it may be useful to demonstrate at least one other option for analyzing the Hansen model in R. To this end, we present the same analysis as above with the package *ouch*. This package was the first to implement the Hansen model in R. It also has one of the fastest (if not *the* fastest) optimization routines for fitting OU models. This speed makes *ouch* adept at analyzing large phylogenies and at simulation-based

analyses, like parametric bootstrapping (see our other tutorial and Boettiger *et al.* [2012]). Moreover, the package has many functions that make it flexible for tailoring analyses, such as simulating a fitted model and calculating the likelihood of user-specified parameters. One downside to *ouch* is that its model assumptions and implementation options are less flexible than those of *OUwie* (see *OUwie*'s documentation for more information). Moreover, its model and phylogeny setup are distinct from nearly all other types of phylogenetic analysis in R, so integration with other R analyses can be challenging. In this tutorial we use a custom function we wrote in order to construct an *ouch* data frame, which contains full information on the phylogeny, including ancestral-state estimates. Our function starts with a tree in the most common phylogeny format (class `phylo`, from the original R phylogeny package *ape*) and uses a vector of ancestral-state estimates in the order output from any ancestral-state estimation routine that uses class `phylo` for phylogenies.

First, let's set up the data for *ouch*. We will make a standard data frame and then use the phylogeny, ancestral-state estimates, and phenotypic data to make the *ouch* data frame. The latter step will use a custom function called `divers_to_ouch()` from Moen *et al.* (2016), who used ancestral-state estimates from the package *diversitree* to make *ouch* data frames. Note that, like *OUwie*, we can use a more complex data frame (e.g. one set up for OU2) to analyze Brownian motion and OU1, so you do not need to make separate data frames for those models.

```
# OU2 (temperate vs. tropical)
dat_ouch_OU2 <- data.frame(dat_OU2, row.names = "species_phylo")
dat_ouch_OU2 <- dat_ouch_OU2[, -3] # ouch does not use SEs
# Now we add the phylogeny and internal-state estimates
dat_ouch_OU2 <- divers_to_ouch(tree_ou2, tree_ou2$node.label, dat_ouch_OU2)

# OU3 (temperate vs. tropical lowland vs. tropical highland)
dat_ouch_OU3 <- data.frame(dat_OU3, row.names = "species_phylo")
dat_ouch_OU3 <- dat_ouch_OU3[, -3]
dat_ouch_OU3 <- divers_to_ouch(tree_ou3, tree_ou3$node.label, dat_ouch_OU3)
```

We should plot our trees to ensure we mapped the ancestral environments properly and see how *ouch* maps node states onto branches (Figs. 2, 3). Plotting in *ouch* is a bit rough, with limited options for improving how it looks, but we can at least see the mapping of internal states. We can also see that *ouch* maps the regime of each branch as the state at its terminal node.

Now we're ready to analyze the models. Note that *ouch* uses a different function for Brownian motion (BM), but this has little consequence on our actual analysis. Remember that we can use the OU2 data frame when analyzing BM because it ignores the 'model' column of selective environments. Moreover, OU1 can use the OU2 data frame (`dat_ouch_OU2`) with just a slight adjustment, by adding a column with `global` as a factor, since we do not need to estimate ancestral states (i.e. all nodes are specified as `global`). Finally, we only need to use a single `ouchtree`, since the function `hansen()` pulls the selective regimes from the data frame, not `ouchtree`.

```
# Set ouchtree for all analyses
ouch_tree <- with(dat_ouch_OU2, ouchtree(nodes, ancestors, times, labels))
# (a) Brownian motion
brown_ouch <- brown(dat_ouch_OU2["CTmin"], ouch_tree)
# (b) Single-optimum OU
dat_ouch_OU2$global <- as.factor("global") # Set single regime for OU1
OU1_ouch <- hansen(dat_ouch_OU2["CTmin"], ouch_tree, regimes = dat_ouch_OU2["global"],
  sqrt.alpha = 1, sigma = 1)
# (c) Temperate-tropical OU2
OU2_ouch <- hansen(dat_ouch_OU2["CTmin"], ouch_tree, regimes = dat_ouch_OU2["model"],
  sqrt.alpha = 1, sigma = 1)
# (d) Highland tropical, lowland tropical, and temperate OU3
```


Figure 2: Map of OU2 regimes for *ouch*. Node numbers are in the same order as the color legend (i.e. 1 = temperate, 2 = tropical).

Figure 3: Map of OU3 regimes for *ouch*. Node numbers correspond to the order of the color legend.

```
OU3_ouch <- hansen(dat_ouch_OU3["CTmin"], ouch_tree, regimes = dat_ouch_OU3["model"],
  sqrt.alpha = 1, sigma = 1)
```

Finally, we summarize the statistical support for the models and then extract the parameter estimates.

```
# Put output objects into a list to more easily summarize results
all_out <- list(brown_ouch, OU1_ouch, OU2_ouch, OU3_ouch)
names(all_out) <- c("BM", "OU1", "OU2", "OU3")

# Summarize model fits
ouch_sum <- map(all_out, summary)
CTmin_fits <- tibble(model = names(all_out), k = map_dbl(ouch_sum, ~.$dof),
  loglik = map_dbl(ouch_sum, ~.$loglik), AICc = map_dbl(ouch_sum, ~.$aic.c),
  wgt = aicc_wgt_calc(AICc))
CTmin_fits # Print summary
```

```
## # A tibble: 4 x 5
##   model      k loglik  AICc    wgt
##   <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 BM         2  -24.7  55.0  0.270
## 2 OU1        3  -26.0  61.5  0.0106
## 3 OU2        4  -19.3  53.2  0.671
## 4 OU3        5  -18.2  58.4  0.0484
```

We see that the statistical support for models varies slightly from our results with *OUwie*. Such differences result from how each package implements the Hansen model. The biggest difference in our analyses is how changes in regimes are mapped onto branches. In *ouch*, any change in regime happens at nodes. So the regime of the terminal node of any branch is the regime for that branch's entire length (Fig. 2, 3). In contrast, in *OUwie* the first half of a branch takes the state of its starting node, while the last half of the same branch takes the state of its terminal node (O'Meara and Beaulieu 2014). While this is the default behavior of *OUwie*, it allows users to adjust where the regime changes along the branch. It is also why *OUwie* seamlessly integrates stochastic character mapping, in which changes occur along branches (see below; Fig. 4). This decision will have a slight effect on the likelihood and a larger effect on parameter estimates.

Let's take a look at the parameter estimates for OU2. Note that `alpha.matrix` and `sigma.sq.matrix` are the source of α and σ^2 , respectively, rather than the first two values given, which are square roots of those parameters.

```
coef(OU2_ouch)

## $sqrt.alpha
## [1] 0.9664801
##
## $sigma
## [1] 2.044915
##
## $theta
## $theta$CTmin
## temperate tropical
## -1.798771 6.572205
##
##
```

```
## $alpha.matrix
##          [,1]
## [1,] 0.9340837
##
## $sigma.sq.matrix
##          [,1]
## [1,] 4.181679
```

Stochastic mapping of internal states of environments (regimes)

As we discuss in our paper, a commonly used option for accommodating uncertainty in ancestral states of the selective environments (regimes) is simulating their evolution on the phylogeny. The simplest way to simulate is to use Bayesian stochastic character mapping (Huelsenbeck *et al.* 2003), known by the acronym SIMMAP and implemented in the package *phytools*.

However, as we emphasized at the beginning of this tutorial, we believe the data from our paper should **not** be analyzed with stochastic mapping or any other ancestral-state estimation method. We simply have too few species for accurate inference, and perhaps most importantly, strongly supported estimates from a previous study already exist. Moreover, users have many options for stochastic mapping. To get a sense for best practices for this method, we encourage readers to consult recent papers (e.g. see citations in our published paper). Our goal here is to simply show researchers how to integrate the **results** of stochastic mapping with the Hansen model. *OUwie* is the only package of which we are aware that can currently do this.

Since our selective environments have discrete states (e.g. temperate, tropical), let's first test models of discrete-character evolution for mapping the states to internal nodes. We will use the function `ace()` from the package *ape* to calculate the likelihood of each model, assuming the transitions between each character state happen at the rates that maximize their likelihood (i.e. MLEs).

```
# OU2: set up data Make a vector of tip states and name them with their
# species' names
states_ou2 <- setNames(dat_OU2[, 2], dat_OU2[, 1])
# Put the data in the same order as the phylogeny
states_ou2 <- states_ou2[tree_ou2$tip.label]
# OU2: Compare models
AIC(ace(states_ou2, tree_ou2, type = "discrete", model = "ER"))
```

```
## [1] 14.54003
```

```
AIC(ace(states_ou2, tree_ou2, type = "discrete", model = "ARD"))
```

```
## [1] 15.62354
```

Let's unpack what we did here. First, we set up the data for analysis. We used an explicit step to reorder the data to the same order as the phylogeny. Normally this is done automatically as an internal check in R phylogenetics functions, but not always, so we do it to be sure. Then, we calculated the likelihood of two models. The first was ER, meaning 'equal rates'. This model forces transitions between temperate and tropical to occur at the same rate. The second was ARD, meaning 'all rates different.' When there are only two states, these two models are our only options. We then compared the models with AIC. AICc surely would be better here, but R has an `AIC()` function that makes direct calculation possible to simplify the tutorial.

The OU3 model is a bit trickier, since three states means that we have more models to consider; there are up to six distinct rates. We'll keep it simple and just consider equal rates, symmetric rates (rates are the

same between any pair of states; three distinct rates), and all rates different (six distinct rates). Everything else is the same as for OU2.

```
# OU3: set up the data
states_ou3 <- setNames(dat_OU3[, 2], dat_OU3[, 1])
states_ou3 <- states_ou3[tree_ou3$tip.label]

# OU3: compare models
ou3_er <- ace(states_ou3, tree_ou3, type = "discrete", model = "ER")
ou3_sym <- ace(states_ou3, tree_ou3, type = "discrete", model = "SYM")
ou3_ard <- ace(states_ou3, tree_ou3, type = "discrete", model = "ARD")
map_dbl(list(ou3_er, ou3_sym, ou3_ard), AIC)
```

```
## [1] 20.96711 24.27796 28.91912
```

The ER model is favored again here (i.e. lowest AIC on the left). Given our sample of 12 species, this result is not surprising, because each additional rate we estimate has a price (in terms of reliable statistical support).

Let's now finally conduct our SIMMAP analysis, using ER for both OU2 and OU3 states. We will simulate 100 replicates. For this tutorial we chose 100 to reduce computation time for our Hansen-model analyses, but many more (at least 1000) will probably give clearer results for your own empirical analysis.

```
set.seed(1978) # To ensure your results look like ours
nsims <- 100 # Number of SIMMAP replicates
simmap_ou2 <- make.simmap(tree_ou2, states_ou2, model = "ER", nsim = nsims)
simmap_ou3 <- make.simmap(tree_ou3, states_ou3, model = "ER", nsim = nsims)
```

Let's plot the first SIMMAP replicate for both OU2 and OU3, to see what we are working with (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Two samples of the stochastic-mapping replicates. On the left is the first SIMMAP replicate for our OU2 model; black branches are estimated as tropical, while grey branches are temperate. On the right is the first SIMMAP replicate for our OU3 environments. Temperate lineages are grey, highland tropical lineages are black, and lowland tropical lineages are blue. Note how SIMMAP allows for changes along branches, rather than just at nodes.

Now we are ready to run our *OUwie* analyses across the SIMMAP replicates. We will not re-fit the Brownian motion or OU1 models, since they do not depend on the simulated internal states. We will also turn off warnings and progress messages so as to not fill up our R console. These analyses will each produce a list of *OUwie* fitted objects, one for each SIMMAP character history.

```
# Temperate-tropical OU2 (loop over SIMMAP trees)
OU2_OUwie_sm <- lapply(simmap_ou2, OUwie, data = dat_OU2, model = "OUM", mserr = "known",
  simmap.tree = T, scaleHeight = T, root.station = T, warn = F, quiet = T,
  algorithm = "invert")

# Temperate-highland-lowland OU3 (loop over SIMMAP trees)
OU3_OUwie_sm <- lapply(simmap_ou3, OUwie, data = dat_OU3, model = "OUM", mserr = "known",
  simmap.tree = T, scaleHeight = T, root.station = T, warn = F, quiet = T,
  algorithm = "invert")
```

To finish, we will summarize our statistical fits across SIMMAP replicates. Normally we would want to calculate statistics for the log-likelihood, but for brevity we will only focus on AICc. We will calculate its mean and 95% confidence interval across SIMMAP replicates.

```
OU2_fits <- tibble(run = seq(nsims), lnL = map_dbl(OU2_OUwie_sm, ~.$loglik),
  AICc = map_dbl(OU2_OUwie_sm, ~.$AICc))
OU3_fits <- tibble(run = seq(nsims), lnL = map_dbl(OU3_OUwie_sm, ~.$loglik),
  AICc = map_dbl(OU3_OUwie_sm, ~.$AICc))
out_table <- data.frame(matrix(nrow = 4, ncol = 4))
colnames(out_table) <- c("model", "AICc_mean", "AICc_2.5", "AIC_97.5")
out_table[, 1] <- c("BM", "OU1", "OU2", "OU3")
out_table[1:2, "AICc_mean"] <- map_dbl(list(brown_OUwie, OU1_OUwie), ~.$AICc)
out_table[3, "AICc_mean"] <- mean(OU2_fits$AICc)
out_table[3, c("AICc_2.5", "AIC_97.5")] <- quantile(OU2_fits$AICc, probs = c(0.025,
  0.975))
out_table[4, "AICc_mean"] <- mean(OU3_fits$AICc)
out_table[4, c("AICc_2.5", "AIC_97.5")] <- quantile(OU3_fits$AICc, probs = c(0.025,
  0.975))
out_table # Print to see results
```

```
##  model AICc_mean AICc_2.5 AIC_97.5
## 1    BM  54.94050      NA      NA
## 2   OU1  61.16954      NA      NA
## 3   OU2  55.08252  53.12482  56.02439
## 4   OU3  60.87294  59.36316  61.40199
```

These results show us that OU2 is still our preferred model on average. But our 95% confidence intervals for OU2 indicate that only under certain ancestral-state reconstructions can we exclude Brownian motion as a better fit to the CT_{\min} data.

We can similarly summarize our parameter estimates. We will just do this for OU2.

```
OU2_params <- data.frame(cbind(t(sapply(OU2_OUwie_sm, function(y) y$solution[1:2,
  1])), t(sapply(OU2_OUwie_sm, function(y) y$theta[, 1]))))
param_table <- data.frame(matrix(nrow = ncol(OU2_params), ncol = 4))
colnames(param_table) <- c("param", "mean", "low95CI", "high95CI")
param_table[, 1] <- c("alpha", "sigma_sq", "temp_theta", "trop_theta")
param_table[, 2] <- apply(OU2_params, 2, mean)
```

```
param_table[, 3:4] <- t(apply(OU2_params, 2, quantile, probs = c(0.025, 0.975)))
param_table # Print to see results
```

```
##      param      mean  low95CI  high95CI
## 1     alpha 2.296016 0.1146781 13.062795
## 2  sigma_sq 9.019565 1.4485206 50.258751
## 3 temp_theta 2.249721 0.9590349  2.630049
## 4 trop_theta 6.479358 6.3507711  6.730507
```

We see that the 95% bounds in α and σ^2 are broad. However, our focus has been on the primary optima, and these analyses show that the optimum for temperate species is always lower than that for tropical species. Moreover, the latter only minimally varies based on estimated ancestral states. We see that

Closing thoughts

We hope this tutorial is helpful for users considering the Hansen model for analyzing physiological data. Our goal with this tutorial was to provide concrete examples of how to use different implementations of the model and options within those implementations. Using phylogenetic comparative methods can be challenging, yet authors of packages are often very responsive to troubleshooting. Moreover, the ‘R-sig-phylo’ mailing list (<https://stat.ethz.ch/mailman/listinfo/r-sig-phylo>) can be helpful to get rapid help from a large community of developers of methods in phylogenetic methods. That said, most problems result from seemingly slight coding errors, so we encourage readers to dig into the basics of data analysis in R if unfamiliar. Finally, analyzing empirical data is a collaborative effort, and often learning happens through seeing the published code of peers. So if you found this tutorial useful, please ensure you make your own code available with any published analysis.

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